

Co-ordination and Atomic Structure.

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The present position of the electronic theory of valency as developed by Kossel, Lewis and Langmuir and applied to simple compounds can be briefly summarised as follows:—

Each atom tends to assume the electronic configuration of the nearest inert gas in a chemical combination with other atoms either by transfer, acceptance or sharing of electrons. This exchange and sharing are confined to the electrons of the outermost layers. These electrons are therefore known as valency electrons. Each valency bond in the case of sharing is supposed to consist of a pair of electrons and is known as co-valence or homœpolar binding. The exchange of electrons gives rise to what is known as electro-valence or heteropolar binding.

This theory in its static form explains quite satisfactorily the valence-phenomena of many elementary atoms specially of the first two short periods, as manifested in their simple compounds. But when considered in the light of later developments regarding the distribution of electrons into groups and sub-groups as illustrated by the work of Bohr (*Nature*, 1923, 112, 29) and specially by that of Smith (*Chem. and Ind.*, 1924, 43, 323) and Stoner (*Phil. Mag.*, 1924, vi, 48, 719) based on the investigations of optical and X-ray spectra of elements, certain difficulties are encountered in the application of this theory to the non-polar compounds like those of carbon.

Following Stoner-Smith's scheme of electron distribution into various sub-groups in the case of carbon and nitrogen for instance—

Atomic Number.	Number of electrons.			
	... K ₁₁	L ₁₁	L ₂₁	L ₃₁
6 C	... 2	2	2	...
7 N	... 2	2	2	1

we find that in compounds like CH₃Cl, CH₂Cl₂, CHCl₃, NH₃OH and many substituted ammonium salts different isomeric types

of molecules might arise due to the possibility of sharing of electrons by any individual atom from different orbital sub-groups in the L-level of carbon and nitrogen—the energy content of this particular atom differing with the position of the carbon or nitrogen electron with which it might share one of its own electrons. Such a differentiation, however small, would at least lend itself to detection by delicate optical methods. Samples of the same substance, chloroform for example, prepared by different methods might have been expected to exhibit this difference, which however is unknown. This may be explained either by assuming that all these substances are equilibrium mixtures of different types of molecules or during combination a redistribution of the electrons occurs which does not permit of any such differentiation. In CHCl_3 , for instance, it may be assumed that the eight-shared electrons between carbon and the other combining atoms are rearranged into two groups of four each in the L-level of carbon, one from each such group entering into every covalent bond. The atoms or groups may then be pictured as arranged at the corners of a regular tetrahedron around the central carbon atom. So the atom returns to the original Bohr grouping for L-level. This latter is the more probable explanation.

The electronic theory of valency in its above simple form fails to account for the formation of the so-called co-ordination compounds by many elements of the transitional groups of Bohr's periodic system. Chromium, iron, cobalt, molybdenum, tungsten, rhodium, palladium, iridium and platinum are the elements specially characterised by this property.

Kossel (*Ann. Phys.*, 1916, **49**, 229) suggests that the formation of complex compounds is due to electrostatic attraction of the central nuclear ion for the surrounding atoms or radicles. According to his view the electro-affinities of ions are not completely saturated in their simple salts or compounds. The unsaturated residual affinity of the central atom then attracts molecules or radicles with atoms having similar residual affinities of an opposite character—the strength of the attraction varying with the charge on the central atom and its radius.

Briggs (*Phil. Mag.*, 1926, *ii*, **11**, 1026) like Kossel in a very ingenious and interesting theory termed as the theory of duplex affinity regards the electrostatic attraction as the cause of complex-formation. And like Werner he introduces the idea of primary and secondary affinities. But his primary and secondary affinities are of different

sign as opposed to those of Werner. According to Briggs a potassium atom for example, which has a tendency to give up an electron and thus change into a positive ion has got a primary positive affinity. But the potassium ion on the other hand, because of the very nature of its being positively charged has a tendency to attract negative electrons or ions and has thus acquired a secondary negative affinity. Similarly chlorine is an element with a primary negative affinity but secondary positive affinity so far as the mutual relationships of the two elements are concerned. Formation of complex compounds is then attributed by him to the exercise of these unsaturated secondary affinities. In a simple compound like carbon tetrachloride, where both the primary and secondary affinities of the combining atoms are completely saturated, the substance becomes non-polar and fails to give rise to any complex formation. Briggs has succeeded in explaining satisfactorily many important properties and characteristics of complex compounds by this simple theory. Though this theory supplies a very plausible explanation of the hidden force that gives rise to complex formation, that is not, however, the only factor that governs such combinations. Had it been so almost all positive elements specially those more electropositive than cobalt and of about the same atomic volume—elements like Be, Mg, Al, Zn, Mn, Cd and Tl should give at least as stable complex compounds as cobalt. This is however not the fact. Similar objections can be raised against Kossel's view as well.

A very important contribution towards elucidation of the structure of co-ordination compounds has been made by Sidgwick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 725), according to whom in the formation of a co-ordination compound the central atom tends to assume the external electronic configuration of the next higher inert gas, the co-ordinated atoms, groups or molecules being held by co-valency to the central nuclear atom. Butler (*Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1925, 21, 349) however does not recognize Sidgwick's interpretation and assumes that the electrons contributed by the co-ordinated units form a distinct group round the central ion. That is, the co-ordination electrons enter the main quantum group next to that represented in the central ion. There is however, no physical conception behind such an assumption and it seems to be more or less speculative.

Sidgwick's view has, however, been supported by Lowry (*Discussion, Farad. Soc.*, "Electronic theory of valency," 1923; *Chem.*

and *Ind*, 1923, **42**, 316), Fowler (*Discussion, Farad Soc*, "Electronic theory of valency," 1923) and Spiers (*Chem and Ind.*, 1923, **42**, 534) and its importance has been revealed by Welo and Baudisch (*Nature*, 1925, **116**, 606). Welo and Baudisch have shown that the complex compounds whose "effective atomic number" is equal to that of the next higher inert gas exhibit diamagnetism due to the formation of closed configuration resembling that of the latter. On the other hand those complexes whose "effective atomic number" is not equal to that of the following inert gas show paramagnetism. Bose (*Zeit Phys*, 1925 **35**, 213, 219) has further assumed that their magnetic moment in Bohr's magneton number are mostly proportional to the difference between their "effective atomic number" and the atomic number of the next higher inert gas. This furnishes a strong evidence in support of Sidgwick's interpretation of the structure of complex compounds. There are however some exceptions specially in the case of less perfect complexes.

Bose (*loc cit*) has proposed a scheme of electron distribution among various subgroups of the main quantum groups for the elements of the first transitional group as well as for their ions, which, according to him satisfactorily explains their magnetic moment. From this he has also developed a scheme of electron distribution for the complex compounds of Cr, Fe, Co, Ni and Cu. But this scheme cannot explain the physical and chemical properties of the complex compounds in all cases as he introduces a differentiation in the coordinated units by placing the shared electron pairs among different subgroups of M and N quantum groups. But as is well known Werner in the case of perfect complexes has definitely proved the equivalence of the six coordinated units which occupy the corners of a regular octahedron and exhibit well defined types of isomerism. This cannot be possible in the case of such a differentiation of the coordinated units.

Another proposal for the electronic configuration of the complex compounds of the first transitional elements has been made by Cabrera (*J Phys Radium*, 1925, **6**, 276) from a consideration of their magnetic moment. This view has been favourably reviewed by Jackson (*Phil Mag*, 1926, **2**, 87). Cabrera's scheme of representation may be regarded as more or less identical with that of Butler, only with this difference that the significance of Sidgwick's rule has not been ignored. According to this scheme a group of 12 electrons divided into 2 subgroups of 6 each representing the 6 coordination units in

the case of sixfold co-ordination compounds or a group of 8 electrons divided into two sub-groups of 4 each for the fourfold co-ordination, are arranged in a separate group after the M- quantum group.

This group of 12 electrons as a whole is supposed to possess no magnetic moment. Cabrera's arrangement does not give an external electronic configuration of the next higher inert gas to the co-ordination complexes and thus deviates from the uniform plan of atom-building process. Further he attributes the same configuration to both Mn^{++} and Fe^{+++} ions but does not explain why ferric iron forms well-defined complexes whereas the corresponding manganous compounds are extremely unstable. The arrangement also suffers from the same defect as was noticed in the case of Butler's proposal having no definite physical conception behind it. Cabrera seems to attach more importance to the total number of electrons than to their configuration.

Before attempting to give any definite electronic configuration to the co-ordination complexes we must thoroughly take into account their physical and chemical properties. From a consideration of these properties it will be found that the complex compounds as a rule can be divided into two main classes depending on their complexity. These can be termed *strong or perfect* and *weak or imperfect* complexes. To the former belong almost all sixfold complexes of cobaltic cobalt, some sixfold complexes of ferrous and ferric iron, all sixfold and fourfold complexes of platinum and the sixfold complexes of chromic chromium, trivalent rhodium, tri- and tetra-valent iridium and a few ruthenium compounds. These are distinguished by their extraordinary complexity and characteristic chemical properties. The rest of the so-called complex compounds coming under the latter head form as it were a transition between true complexes and the double or associated compounds. To the former, therefore, we can very reasonably ascribe a more or less inert gas configuration in accordance with Sidgwick's interpretation.

First of all we must consider the electronic arrangement in the transitional elements and in their simple ions. No definite or fixed arrangement can be regarded here as satisfactory and sufficient to explain all their physical and chemical properties. This is the reason why a number of different schemes of grouping have been proposed by different investigators. Besides Smith-Stoner's original scheme, others like those of Swinne (*Zeit. Elektrochem.*, 1925, **31**, 417), Bose (*loc. cit.*), Samuel and Markowicz (*Zeit. Phys.*, 1926, **38**,

22), Lessheim and Samuel (*Zeit. Phys.*, 1926, 40, 220) for the transitional elements of the first group may be mentioned in this connection. In fact it may be assumed with some reason that in these elements or in their ions the electrons in the M_3 -level are rather mobile and prone to ready rearrangement between the two sub-groups under external chemical influences. In the case of certain elementary ions it may further be assumed that there is an equilibrium mixture of two or more types with different arrangement of electrons in the M_3 sub-groups, or in other words, such ions may be regarded after Swinne as a mixture of "electronic isomers" in equilibrium. In fact the magnetic moment curve for the ions of the transitional elements of the first group shows some pronounced irregularities in the region corresponding to iron and cobalt ions. Following electron-distribution for these elements is in better accord with their chemical behaviour than any other previously proposed and it has the further advantage of explaining the formation of co-ordination complexes without much difficulty (Table I). As for the magnetic moment of the ions, we can under the present circumstances simply hold after Ladenburg (*Naturwissenschaften*, 1920 8, 6) that it is only the incompleted groups that contribute to this effect. Following simple assumptions are made in formulating this scheme. A odd electron in the $M_{3,1}$ sub-group is very mobile specially at the commencement of the formation of the group and readily acts as a valency electron whereas every two electrons tend to produce a more or less stable coupling. The stability of a group on the whole increases with the number of electrons in it.

Reference may be made in this connection to Hund's (*Zeit. Phys.*, 1925, 33, 362) distribution of electrons based upon an analysis of the complicated spectra of these elements. Hund does not distinguish between the $M_{3,1}$ and $M_{3,2}$ sub-groups, i.e., he does not split up the M_3 electrons into two sub-levels. But as such a sub-division is necessary from the chemical standpoint, it is quite reasonable to assume that the M_3 group may split up into $M_{3,1}$ and $M_{3,2}$ in more than one way during chemical union depending upon external conditions and the mode of combination. We may thus regard the atom as passing into an active phase during chemical union. In Table I we stick to Hund's (*loc. cit.*) distribution for the neutral atoms. In the case of cobaltic ion it will be noticed that it behaves as a mixture of two electronic isomers which thus accounts for its anomalous magnetic behaviour.

TABLE I.

Atoms and ions.	Electron number.	Number of electrons in different groups.				Bohr's magneton number.
		K _{1,1} to M _{2,2}	M _{3,3}	M _{4,4}	N _{1,1}	
Cr	24	18	...	4	2	
Cr ⁺⁺	22	18	3	...	1	4
Cr ⁺⁺⁺	21	18	3	...		3
Mn	25	18	...	6	2	
Mn ⁺⁺	23	18	1	...	4	5
Fe	26	18	...	6	2	
Fe ⁺⁺	24	18	3	...	3	4
Fe ⁺⁺⁺	23	18	3	...	2	5
Co	27	18	...	7	2	
Co ⁺⁺	25	18	3	...	4	4
Co ⁺⁺⁺	24	18	(a) 4	...	2	2.5
			(b) 3	...	3	(Weber, <i>Ann. Phys.</i> , 1911, 36, 624)
Ni	28	18	...	8	2	
Ni ⁺⁺	26	18	4	...	4	2
Cu	29	18	...	9	2	
Cu ⁺	28	18	4	...	6	Diamagnetic.
Cu ⁺⁺	27	18	4	...	5	1

We shall now proceed to discuss the formation of co-ordination complexes by the ions with electronic configurations as described in Table I. In the first place, we shall deal only with the strong sixfold complexes. Their electronic configurations are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Name of the Complex.	Number of electrons in various groups.					Number of Bohr's magneton.
	K _{1,1} to M _{2,2}	M _{3,3}	M _{4,4}	N _{1,1}	N ₂	
Cr ⁺⁺⁺ complex	18	3	6		6	3
Fe ⁺⁺ complex	18	4	6	2	6	Diamagnetic.
Fe ⁺⁺⁺ complex	18	4	6	1	6	1
Co ⁺⁺⁺ complex	18	4	6	2	6	Diamagnetic.

In this scheme it will be noticed that the 12 electrons supplied by the six co-ordinating units arrange themselves in 6 pairs of orbits belonging to the $M_{3,3}$ sub-group and N_2 group. It is assumed here that the N_2 group had no occasion to split up into two sub-groups $N_{2,1}$ and $N_{2,2}$, as it had previously no electron of its own supplied by the central ion. Every one electronic orbit of $M_{3,3}$ is thus coupled with one of N_2 to form a pair of shared orbits for each co-ordinating unit of the sixfold complexes. This maintains the equivalence of the six units and does not give rise to any differentiation whatsoever. They are thus symmetrically arranged around the corners of a regular octahedron as required by Werner's theory. The configuration thus produced resembles closely that of the next inert gas krypton specially in the case of diamagnetic cobaltic and ferrous complexes, excepting that the electrons of the $M_{3,3}$ and N_2 groups are not in the sole possession of the central atom but equally shared between it and the associating units. Ionizable atoms thus bound, as for instance chlorine in chloropentamine complexes can not easily come out as ions as it shares electrons from a now comparatively inner level like $M_{3,3}$. This is specially noticeable in the case of cobaltic and ferrous complexes where $N_{1,1}$ group is completely filled up, which further stabilizes the $M_{3,3}$ subgroup. The electrons in $N_{1,1}$ group cannot further act as valency electrons because of a shielding layer of N_2 electrons.

Now if we analyse the mechanism of formation and the stability of these complexes it will be observed that manganese complexes of the perfect type are either incapable of formation or even if formed will be extremely unstable. Taking the case of cobalt first, we find from the table that the cobaltic ion is assumed to be an equilibrium mixture of two electronic isomers (a) and (b). One (a) has the electron distribution of 4 in $M_{3,3}$ and 2 in $M_{3,3}$. This is the configuration most active in the complex formation. The other arrangement (b) with 3 electrons in $M_{3,3}$ and 3 in $M_{3,3}$ represents its ordinary chemical behaviour and its instability. Free cobaltic ion is known to change readily into the cobaltous one. Now in the (a) phase of the cobaltic ion the $M_{3,3}$ group is complete and there are only 2 electrons in $M_{3,3}$. Under the influence of strongly polar molecules, groups or ions, these are pushed out to the now vacant $N_{1,1}$ level thus completing the latter and at the same time both the $M_{3,3}$ and N_2 levels are filled up by the sharing of electrons with the co-ordinating units. On the other hand,

cobaltous ion is incapable of forming such strong sixfold complexes. This is evident from its electron distribution. In this there are 3 electrons in the $M_{3,}$ and 4 in the $M_{3,}$ subgroups. Now 4 electrons in the $M_{3,}$ level form a comparatively stable grouping. Besides there will be no accommodation for the six shared electrons in it even if two of the four electrons of the $M_{3,}$ level be shifted to $N_{1,}$ and one to $M_{3,}$ level — there being still one electron left in $M_{3,}$. Only under the influence of powerfully polarised co-ordinating ions like -CN this last electron can be forced out of $M_{3,}$ to a distant outer level to form a compound like potassium cobaltocyanide, but the latter becomes thereby extremely unstable and this lone electron will readily act as a valency electron leading to the oxidation of the cobaltocyanide to cobalticyanide. This is what actually happens. Potassium cobaltocyanide as is well known is oxidized even by water with evolution of hydrogen gas.

Turning to the iron complexes it will be noticed that the configuration of the ferrous complex indicates a perfectly stable one resembling that of the next inert gas krypton. But the formation of ferrous complex can not take place easily. Since there is a group of 3 electrons in $M_{3,}$ level of ferrous iron, of which only two can be knocked out to $N_{1,}$ level, there will still remain one. This can only find place in $M_{3,}$ level. But only the action of strongly co-ordinating polar substances like α -dipyridyl molecules and cyanogen ions can compel this last electron to move back to $M_{3,}$ specially as the charge on the ferrous ion is comparatively low amounting to two units only. Hence we are acquainted with compounds like potassium ferrocyanide but with no positive ammoniacal complexes like hexammine, pentammine or tetrammine salts. Ferric complexes from the very nature of their configuration will be unstable having one lone electron in the $N_{1,}$ level which tends to stabilize itself readily coupling with a second electron. α -dipyridyl ferric complex, as is well-known, readily passes into the ferrous complex and potassium ferricyanide for this reason acts as a powerful oxidizing agent. On the other hand we know that simple ferrous ion readily passes into the ferric state owing to the former's having one odd electron in the $M_{3,}$ level.

Manganese ion having a fairly stable grouping of 4 electrons in the $M_{3,}$ level fails to produce any stable complex compound. And we are aware of only very unstable mangano- and mangani-cyanides. It appears that in any sub-group the stability increases with the

number of electrons as it becomes gradually filled up and an odd electron has a tendency to act like a valency electron or form a close couple with another.

Chromium complexes are more readily formed as the $M_{3,3}$ level being vacant is fully available for sharing. The complexes are therefore fairly stable on account of their more or less symmetrical external configuration. They are however much less stable than the corresponding cobalt compounds due to their $N_{1,1}$ level remaining unoccupied. Chromous ion having a low valency cannot give rise to a stable complex specially as the odd electron in $M_{3,3}$ would add to the instability.

Now we shall take up the cases of perfect sixfold complexes of molybdenum, rhodium, iridium and platinum. The electron distribution in their atoms, ions and corresponding complexes are given in Table III. As before we follow Hund's scheme for the neutral atoms.

TABLE III.

Name.	Number of electrons in various groups.					Bohr's magneton number.
	$K_{1,1}$ to $N_{2,2}$	$N_{3,3}$	$N_{3,3}$	$O_{1,1}$	O_6	
42 Mo	36	... 4	...	2	...	
Mo ⁺⁺⁺	36	3	
Mo ⁺⁺⁺ complex	36	3	6	...	6	3 (Rāy and Bhar, <i>private communication</i>).
45 Rb	36	... 7	...	2	...	
Rh ⁺⁺⁺	36	4	2	
Rh ⁺⁺⁺ complex	36	4	6	2	6	Diamagnetic.

Table III continued.

Name.	Number of electrons in various groups.					Bohr's magneton number.
	K _{1,1} to O _{2,2}	O _{3,2}	O _{4,2}	P _{1,1}	P ₁	
77 Ir	68		7 0	2		
Ir ⁺⁺⁺	68	4	2	0		
Ir ⁺⁺⁺ complex	68	4	6	2	6	Diamagnetic.
Ir ⁺⁺⁺⁺	68	3	2	0		
Ir ⁺⁺⁺⁺ complex	68	4	6	1	6	
78 Pt	68		8 0	2		
Pt ⁺⁺⁺⁺	68	0	6	0		Diamagnetic (Ráy and Bhar, <i>private communication</i>).
Pt ⁺⁺⁺⁺ complex	68	4	6	2	6	Diamagnetic.

It will be found that the trivalent iridium, rhodium and tetravalent platinum complexes possess quite closed configurations like the cobalt complex and hence they will be as stable as the latter and will be likewise diamagnetic. This is in close agreement with facts as far as they are known (Rosenbohm, *Zeit. phys. Chem.*, 1919, **93**, 693). Tetravalent iridium complexes having a lone electron in N_{1,1} subgroup resemble ferric complexes and like the latter are comparatively unstable and are known only in the case of a few strongly associating units.

Molybdenum complexes having a configuration similar to that of chromium complexes behave like the latter.

Finally some eightfold stable co-ordination complexes of molybdenum and tungsten as well as some fourfold stable complexes of palladium and platinum need be discussed here. The following types of very stable compounds of Mo and W are known.

Possible electronic configurations for these compounds are represented in Table IV below.

Table IV.

Name.	Number of electrons in various groups.				
	K _{1,1} to N _{2,2}	N _{3,3}	N _{2,2}	O _{1,1}	O ₂
42 Mo	36	4	..	2	...
Mo ⁺⁺⁺⁺	36	...	2
Mo ⁺⁺⁺⁺ complex	36	4	6	2	6
	K _{1,1} to O _{2,2}	O _{3,2}	O _{3,3}	P _{1,1}	P ₂
74 W	68	4	...	2	...
W ⁺⁺⁺⁺	68	...	2
W ⁺⁺⁺⁺ complex	68	4	6	2	6
W ⁺⁺⁺⁺⁺	68	...	1
W ⁺⁺⁺⁺⁺ complex	68	4	6	1	6

As regards the positive ions of molybdenum and tungsten nothing can be definitely stated about their configurations—in fact there are no free positive ions of Mo and W known in solution as the electro-positive character of these elements is very weak. Simple compounds of Mo and W can be more appropriately regarded as nonpolar compounds. It is for this reason that they form no positive complexes—all molybdenum and tungsten complexes being electro-negative or neutral in character. The configurations of the ions of these elements represented in the above table are meant only to indicate the mechanism of formation of the corresponding complexes. Here as usual 12 out of the 16 shared electrons are equally distributed either between the N_{3,3} and O₂ levels in the case of molybdenum or between O_{3,3} and P₂ levels in tungsten. The rest four goes to N_{2,2} in molybdenum or to O_{3,3} in tungsten. In the case of pentavalent tungsten complex, there is one lone electron in P_{1,1}. This makes them somewhat less stable. From the nature of the configuration it can be expected that the pentavalent tungsten complexes should exhibit paramagnetism while both the tetravalent Mo and W complexes would be diamagnetic. This has yet to be proved.

We now pass on to the fourfold stable complexes of palladium and platinum, their configurations being shown in Table V.

In these fourfold complexes the 8 shared electrons are distributed equally between $N_{3,2}$ and $O_{3,2}$, or between $O_{3,2}$ and $P_{2,2}$. Such compounds should be diamagnetic. This is borne out by facts.

Table V.

Name.	Number of electrons in various groups.					
	$K_{1,1}$ to $N_{2,2}$	$N_{3,2}$	$N_{3,3}$	$O_{1,1}$	$O_{2,1}$	$O_{3,2}$
46 Pd	36		10			
Pd ⁺⁺	36	...	6	2		
Pd ⁺⁺ complex	...	4	6	2		4
	$K_{1,1}$ to $O_{2,2}$	$O_{3,2}$	$O_{3,3}$	$P_{1,1}$	$P_{2,1}$	$P_{2,2}$
78 Pt	68	...	10
Pt ⁺⁺	68	...	6	2
Pt ⁺⁺ complex	68	4	6	2	...	4 Diamagnetic

From an examination of the electronic distribution in all the complexes discussed above it will be observed that the electronic orbits of the co-ordinating atoms are likely to be considerably strained or distorted due to the sharing of electrons with the central ion in different levels. That such a distortion of orbits does take place has been assumed by Fajans (*Naturwissenschaften*, 1923, 11, 165), even in the case of many simple compounds. Meisenheimer (*Zeit. phys. Chem.*, 1921, 97, 304) regards this distortion of orbits as the cause of colour in chemical compounds. In the case of complex compounds it is observed that the colour of the central ion is profoundly altered by co-ordination and the colour of the complex also varies characteristically with the nature of the associated units. Thus a co-ordinated nitrogen atom in the form of NH_3 or NO_2 group tends to develop a yellow colour in the complex as in hexammine salts and cobaltinitrites; a sulphur atom in association as SO_3 radical produces brown

to yellowish brown colour and an oxygen atom as in CO_2 or SO_2 radical gives rise to violet to red-violet colour; halogen atoms as in chloropentammine compounds produce carmine red colour. This colour change according to Meisenheimer (*loc. cit.*) is due to the distortion of the electronic orbits. And this distortion of orbits can be easily accounted for if we assume the scheme depicted above for the configuration of the complexes. As in them every two electrons of each shared pair enter two different levels of the central ion,—a condition most likely to lead to a considerable distortion of the electronic orbits of the co-ordinated groups. This becomes a source of great strain in the complex. It makes them somewhat less stable than the simple non-polar compounds.

Last of all we shall discuss the case of the weak or imperfect complexes. To this class belong almost all complex compounds of nickel, copper, zinc, cadmium, cobaltous cobalt and various other elements. Compounds of this class, *e.g.*, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{NH}_3$, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$, $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$, $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{NH}_3$, etc., more or less easily lose their complex character even by thermal or other physical disturbances. Hydrates like $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ etc. may be included in this class. Their stepwise dissociation with rise of temperature as determined by Biltz and Huttig (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1922 123, 42) points to a differentiation among the associated units, which shews that all the associated units are not equally strongly held by the central ion. So in their case, it quite stands to reason to assume that the different units share electrons with the central ion at different levels. Thus in the case of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{NH}_3$ for instance all the five ammonia molecules have not the same binding strength. One or two of them may share electrons in one single level, another in another level and a third in a still different level and so on. This is demonstrated by the following electron distribution in them (Table VI).

The magnetic moment of these complexes according to this scheme should remain practically unchanged. This is actually borne out by facts as indicated by the last column. Almost all determinations of the magnetic moment of these compounds indicate that the values depend entirely on the paramagnetic ion and are not influenced by association (Rosenbohm, *Zeit. phys. Chem.*, 1919, 93, 693). In some instances as in fourfold nickel complexes the magnetic moment has been found to be somewhat less than that of the free central ion. This may be due to some rearrangement

giving rise to a more stable configuration as suggested by Cabrera and shown below:—

	Number of electrons.				
	K_{11} to M_{22}^-	M_{32}	M_{33}	$(N_1$ to $N_4)$	
Ni ⁺⁺	18	4	4
Fourfold Ni ⁺⁺ complex	18	4	4	4	4

TABLE VI.

Name.	Number of electrons in different levels:									Bohr's magneton number.
	K_{11} to M_{22}^-	M_{32}	M_{33}	N_{11}	N_{21}	N_{22}	N_{32}	O_{11}		
Co ⁺⁺	... 18	3	4	4
Co ⁺⁺ complex (fourfold)	... 18	3	4	2	2	4	4
Co ⁺⁺ complex (sixfold)	... 18	3	4	2	2	4	4	4
Ni ⁺⁺	... 18	4	4	2
Ni ⁺⁺ complex (fourfold)	... 18	4	4	2	2	4	2
Ni ⁺⁺ complex (sixfold)	... 18	4	4	2	2	4	4	2
Cu ⁺⁺	... 18	4	5	1
Cu ⁺⁺ complex (fourfold)	... 18	4	5	2	2	4	1
Cu ⁺⁺ complex (fivefold)	... 18	4	5	2	2	4	2	1
Cu ⁺⁺ complex (sixfold)	... 18	4	5	2	2	4	4	1

In this case the 8 electrons supplied by the four associating units possibly rearrange themselves in part at least into two groups of 4 each, each binding unit furnishing one electron to each group. A more symmetrical arrangement is thus developed but involving an increased distortion of orbits which is likely to influence the magnetic moment. Such a redistribution leads to the tetrahedral

arrangement of the associated units as in the case of carbon compounds discussed in the beginning. Strongly associating units like dimethylglyoxime, $\beta\beta\beta'$ -triamino-triethylamine are likely to assist this redistribution.

In the light of above discussion this type of imperfect complexes may be termed "Associated Complexes" and consequently the perfect class as "Penetration Complexes" since in the latter case a more or less inner level of electrons takes part in the sharing.

Summary.

In summing up the discussion I would like to emphasise the following points.

Three factors governing the formation of complex compounds should be recognized:

- (a) Charge on the central ion which is the source of attraction.
- (b) Tendency of the central ion to assume the next higher inert gas configuration.
- (c) The nature of the electron distribution in the central ion.

In the case of penetration or strong complexes both the factors (a) and (b) operate strongly; the third factor (c) acts as a controlling factor and determines the nature of the complex formation and the type of co-ordination.

The factor (a) also involves the influence of the volume of the ion—the smaller is the volume, the stronger is the attraction.

In discussing the electron-distribution in the central ion from the chemical standpoint the following simple assumptions were made and found very useful.

Every two electrons tend to couple closely. A lone electron in a comparatively outer subgroup is rather unstable. The stability of any subgroup increases with the number of electrons in it.

From these assumptions a scheme for electron-distribution in strong and weak complexes has been suggested. Tendency to assume the external electronic configuration of the next higher inert gas by the central ion is upheld as the main guiding factor in the formation of penetration or perfect complexes.

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Note.—Since this paper was completed in April, 1927 some other papers have appeared on the subject. Prof. Ladenburg in a lecture before the German Chemical Society (*Zeit. phys. Chem.*, 1927, 126, 133) expressed the view that two types of co-ordinated compounds should be recognized,—stable and less stable. The diamagnetism of a complex compound according to him arises from the complete filling up of the intermediate sub-groups of the central atom with electrons. This is in agreement with the view elaborated in this paper.

Two other papers on "Co-ordination bond and atomic structure" have also been published lately by Lessheim, Meyer and Samuel (*Zeit. Physik*, 1927, 43, 199; *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 165, 253). According to these authors co-ordinative binding is effected by the electrons of the outermost completely filled up sub-group ("Teilunter" group). They assume one electron bond which is rather unique and take no cognisance of Sidgwick's conception. What is specially objectionable in their view is that they make an atom which has already completed its octet or assumed an inert gas configuration (as for instance N atom in NH_3 mol) to share a further electron supplied by the central ion thus making the total number of electrons round the nitrogen atom eleven which is most unlikely.

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